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FURTHER EVIDENCE OF DISHONEST SCIENTIFIC REPORTING AND DATA FALSIFICATION IN THE CLINICAL TRIAL OF THE ANTI-SARS-COV-2/COVID-19 VACCINE DEVELOPED BY ASTRA ZENECA/UNIVERSITY OF OXFORD.

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Abstract.

It was previously reported that there was evidence of Dishonest Scientific Reporting and Data Falsification in the clinical trial of the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine developed by Astra Zeneca/University of Oxford. Despite the fact that the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine developed by Astra Zeneca/University of Oxford has been approved for use in Europe, there is a paucity of scientific data that show that the said vaccine is effective and safe. It is not clear why the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine developed by Astra Zeneca/University of Oxford has not been approved in the United States of America. Here, through the analysis of the paper entitled "Safety and efficacy of the ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 vaccine (AZD1222) against SARS-COV-2: an interim analysis of four randomized controlled trials in Brazil, South Africa, and the UK ", by Voysey, M. et al. and published in Lancet [Lancet (2021) Vol. 397, pp99-111], further evidence is provided that there are Dishonest Scientific Reporting and Data Falsification in the said clinical trial. In particular, it is shown that the IPUV-10000 Number (Total Number of Individuals Infected with SARS-COV-2 Per 10000 Unvaccinated Population) and IPV-10000 Number (Total Number of Individuals

Infected with SARS-COV-2 Per 10000 Vaccinated Population) calculated from the data in the paper Voysey, M. et al. do not reflect real life prevailing SARS-COV-2/COVID-19 pandemic situation. There are alarming discrepancies between the values calculated from the data presented by Voysey et al. and data from real life prevailing SARS-COV-2/COVID-19 pandemic situation, and data presented by clinical trials of other anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccines developed by Pfizer/BioNTech, Moderna and Johnson & Johnson.

On or around March 22, 2021, the United States National Institute of Health (NIH) issued a press release [1] stating that "Investigational AstraZeneca vaccine prevents COVID-19". No scientific data from any clinical trial was presented. One the same day, AstraZeneca announced on its website that its anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine developed in collaboration with the University of Oxford, AZD1222 was 79% efficacious at preventing symptomatic COVID-19 and 100% efficacious at preventing severe or critical disease and hospitalization [2]. However, no scientific data was presented neither by the NIH nor AstraZeneca. It appears that the NIH has become an advertising agency for selling unproven snake oil type remedies. Subsequently, the Director of the United States National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases (NIAID) seemed to distance himself from the NIH and AstraZeneca when he stated that the data in AstraZeneca's public statement "were somewhat outdated and might, in fact, be misleading a bit" [3]. In effect, the Director of the NIAID is saying that AstraZeneca/University of Oxford have committed Dishonest Scientific Reporting and Data Falsification. Perhaps more troubling is the fact the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine developed by AstraZeneca/University of Oxford has still not received approval in the United States of America and is being distributed to the whole world.

Dishonest Scientific Reporting is defined by the following: (i) selective reporting of data to arrive at a conclusion that fits one's hypothesis, (ii) falsely reporting that one has performed some experiments when one had not, (iii) not reporting what one has performed to arrive at a conclusion that fits one hypothesis, and (iv) not reporting that some experiments and results reported in one's paper or thesis were performed by someone else or unknown person [5,6]. Data Falsification is defined by the following: (i) Designing an experiment by manipulation equipment or methodologies so that it would produce specific results that would fit one's conclusion and hypothesis, (ii) Deliberately excluding experiments and data that contradict one's conclusion and

hypothesis, and (iii) Manipulating data so that the manipulated data does not represent the actual and true results [5,6]. Data Fabrication is defined as the manufacture of data that did not come from an actual experiment but from one's own imagination (i.e. no experiments were performed or no analysis and interpretation of available scientific data was performed [5,6]. Did AstraZeneca/University of Oxford commit Dishonest Scientific Reporting and Data Falsification with respect to clinical trial of its anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine (AZD1222). It is highly unscientific and suspicious that AstraZeneca/University of Oxford has chosen not to publish its latest anti-SARS-COV-2 clinical trial while it is selling and distributing the said vaccine to the entire world. It is indeed not clear why the United States Federal Drug Administration has so far not approved the use of the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine developed by AstraZeneca/University of Oxford while it plans to distribute it for use in some other countries [6]. Here, through the analysis of the paper entitled "Safety and efficacy of the ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 vaccine (AZD1222) against SARS-COV-2: an interim analysis of four randomized controlled trials in Brazil, South Africa, and the UK ", by Voysey, M. et al. and published in Lancet [Lancet (2021) Vol. 397, pp99-111], it is shown that there are Dishonest Scientific Reporting and Data Falsification in the said clinical trial.

Voysey, M. et al. [7] reported that the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine (AZD1222) developed by AstraZeneca/University of Oxford is ~60.3 % efficacious in a clinical trial with a standard protocol of 2 doses (5×10^{10} viral particles) that took place in the United Kingdom because of the finding that 38 individuals out of total of 2430 unvaccinated subjects were infected with SARS-COV-2 and 15 individuals out of a total of 2377 vaccinated subjects. The value of ~60.3 % efficacy was arrived at by subtracting the number of infections in vaccinated subjects from the number of infections from unvaccinated subjects and multiplying by 100 which is quite misleading and calculated to deceive the reader as it does not state whether the unvaccinated and vaccinated subjects were all experiencing real life prevailing SARS-COV-2/COVID-19 pandemic condition. In the same clinical trial, apparently due to a mistake of dosing, Voysey, M. et al [7] reported a 90.0 % efficacy for the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine (AZD1222) developed by AstraZeneca/University of Oxford on account of the fact that in a protocol of lower dose followed by a standard protocol dose, 30 individuals out of 1374 unvaccinated subjects were infected with SARS-COV-2 and 3 individuals of 1367 vaccinated subjects. From these data, one can determine that the IPUV-10000 and IPV-10000 Numbers for those subjects who did not receive and those

who did receive the standard protocol of 2 equal doses of anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine are ~156 and ~63 respectively and the IPUV-10000 and IPV-10000 Numbers for those subjects who did not receive and those who did receive the mistaken non-protocol of 2 unequal doses of anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine are ~128 and ~22 respectively.

Figure 1. IPUV-10000 Number for the standard dose (I) and non-standard dose (II) of the clinical trial of the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine (AZD-1222) developed by AstraZeneca/University of Oxford.

At first glance, these results would tend to suggest that the non-standard protocol of one lower dose followed by a standard protocol dose was superior as it was reported to achieve 90.0 % efficacy. However, for those who read the whole paper with their brain and understand statistics, it can be seen that there is a major discrepancy in the IPUV-10000 Numbers for the standard protocol consisting of two equal doses and the non-standard protocol consisting of a first lower dose followed by a second standard protocol dose (Figure 1). IPUV-10000 Numbers for both should be the same or very similar. The fact that they are not means that the experimental design was not only faulty but there has been Dishonest Scientific Reporting and Data Falsification. What is more worrisome is that the placebos are themselves dangerous to the subjects. The placebos were associated with IPUV-10000 Numbers of ~159 and ~128 for the standard protocol and non-standard protocol respectively (Figure 1). These results show that the placebo (whatever it

contains! It is clear that the same placebo of Meningococcal Group A, C, W and Y conjugate vaccine was used for both first and second dose in the standard protocol but not in the non-standard protocol) in the standard protocol cause ~24% increase of SARS-COV-2 infection in unvaccinated subjects when compared to the non-standard protocol. The increase of SARS-COV-2 infection among unvaccinated subjects would constitute Scientific Misconduct [4,5] and would also be a violation of the Nuremberg Declaration as it would constitute unethical treatment of human subjects.

If the clinical trial of the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine developed by AstraZeneca/University of Oxford was designed and conducted under prevailing real-life SARS-COV-2/COVID-19 pandemic condition, the IPUV-10000 Numbers for the standard protocol and non-standard protocol, and the IPUV Numbers in the general population should be very similar since the subjects who have not been vaccinated should all experience similar rate of SARS-COV-2 infections. Figure 2 compares the IPUV-10000 Numbers in the general population in the United Kingdom and in the subjects of the clinical trial described by Voysey, M. et al. [7]. The results show that the IPUV-10000 Numbers calculated from the data presented by Voysey, M. et al. [7] are quite anomalous. The results strongly suggest that the clinical trial of of the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine developed by AstraZeneca/University of Oxford was not properly designed and not conducted under prevailing real-life SARS-COV-2/COVID-19 pandemic condition.

Figure 2. IPUV-10000 Number for the standard dose (I), non-standard dose (II) of the clinical trial of the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine (AZD-1222) developed by AstraZeneca/University of Oxford and IPUV-10000 Number for the general unvaccinated population of the United Kingdom from April 2020 to January 2021.

There are major discrepancies in the IPUV-10000 Numbers calculated from the data presented in the clinical trials of anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccines developed by Pfizer/BioNTech [7], Moderna [8], Johnson & Johnson [9] and AstraZeneca/University of Oxford [7] (Figure 3). It was previously reported that only the IPUV-10000 Number calculated from the clinical trial of the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine developed by Johnson & Johnson reflected more closely prevailing real-life SARS-COV-2/COVID-19 pandemic condition in the United States [11]. The data presented by Voysey, M. et al. [7] for the clinical trial of the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine developed by AstraZeneca/University of Oxford shows that the said clinical trial was not conducted prevailing real-life SARS-COV-2/COVID-19 pandemic condition.

Figure 1. IPUV-10000 Numbers for the clinical trials of the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccines developed by AstraZeneca/University of Oxford (I and II), Pfizer/BioNTech, Moderna and Johnson & Johnson. The IPUV-10000 Numbers for Pfizer/BioNTech, Moderna and Johnson & Johnson are from [11].

Voysey, M. et al. [7] also provided results for the effects of the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine developed by AstraZeneca/University of Oxford on the incidence of SARS-COV-2 infection and prevention of COVID-19 symptoms in Brazil and South Africa. Unfortunately, these results cannot be taken at face value as Voysey, M. et al. [7] readily admit that as opposed to what occurred in the United Kingdom, "In Brazil, there was no testing plan for asymptomatic infections. In South Africa, asymptomatic infections were detected from swabs obtained at study visits attended, but are not summarized here as there were only a small number of timepoints for detection of these cases" and did not provide any information how symptomatic infections were recorded and studied in Brazil and South Africa.

Another major deficiency in the clinical trial of the the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine developed by AstraZeneca/University of Oxford is that not enough volunteers were recruited. Voysey, M. et al. [7] would like the reader to believe that it is possible to determine the efficacy and safety of an anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine by recruiting only 3804 unvaccinated and 3744 individuals. Voysey,

M. et al. [7] could not determine whether the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine developed by AstraZeneca/University of Oxford can prevent death due to SARS-COV-2 infection and COVID-19. As a comparison, despite recruiting more than 30,000 study subjects, the clinical trials of the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccines developed by Pfizer/BioNTech, Moderna, and Johnson & Johnson [8-10] were unable to state whether their vaccines can prevent death due SARS-COV-2 infection and COVID-19 or not. It is interesting to note that a recent study by Walach, H, et al. [12,13] stated that " COVID-19 vaccines have had expedited reviews without sufficient safety data," and determined that " for three deaths prevented by vaccinations we have to accept two inflicted by vaccinations " with respect to the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine developed by Pfizer/BioNTech.

In conclusion, based on the above, it can be stated without reservation that the clinical trial of the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine (AZD1222) developed by AstraZeneca/University of Oxford [7] is riddled with Dishonest Scientific Reported and Data Falsification. The clinical trial of the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine (AZD1222) developed by AstraZeneca/University of Oxford [7] was designed to confuse and mislead, and to produce specific results that would support the conclusion that the said vaccine was effective and safe when it has not been or cannot be proven to be so. The data presented by Voysey, M. et al. [7] shows major discrepancy in the calculated IPUV-10000 Numbers of the standard protocol and the non-standard protocol which was apparently arrived at by mistake. The data presented by Voysey, M. et al. [7] shows that the Placebos (Meningococcal Group A, C, W and Y and/or Saline) are harmful to the unvaccinated participants. IPUV-10000 Numbers for both should be the same or very similar but are not. The placebos were associated with IPUV-10000 Numbers of ~159 and ~128 for the standard protocol and non-standard protocol respectively. The fact that the IPUV-10000 Numbers are different means that the experimental design was not only faulty but there has been Dishonest Scientific Reporting and Data Falsification. It is also not clear why in the United Kingdom, the non-standard protocol (COV003) used Meningococcal Group A, C, W and Y conjugate vaccine as placebo in the first dose and saline as placebo for the second dose whereas the standard protocol (COV002) used Meningococcal Group A, C, W and Y conjugate vaccine as placebo in both the first and second dose. Is it because of incompetence or purposeful design? The efficacy and safety of the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine (AZD1222) is therefore highly questionable. The conclusions of Walach, H, et al. [12,13] with respect to the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine developed by Pfizer/BioNTech

should also apply to the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine (AZD1222) developed by AstraZeneca/University of Oxford.

No data of DPUV-10000 (Total Number of Deaths of Individuals Infected With SARS-COV-2 and Developing COVID-19 Per 10000 Unvaccinated Population) and DPV-10000 (Total Number of Deaths of Individuals Infected With SARS-COV-2 and Developing COVID-19 Per 10000 Vaccinated Population) could be calculated because too few subjects were recruited for the clinical trial [7]. It is mind-boggling, unscientific, sheer incompetency and tragic that Voysey, M. et al. [7] would assume that the clinical trial of the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine (AZD1222) that recruited 7548 participants in the United Kingdom for two set of protocols could determine whether the said vaccine was effective and safe. Even more surprising and perhaps criminal is that the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine (AZD1222) developed by AstraZeneca/University of Oxford has been injected into millions all over the world. The finding of alarming breakthrough infections and deaths (being blamed on the SARS-COV-2 variant, B.1.617.2 from India) in the United Kingdom of individuals vaccinated with the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine (AZD1222) developed by AstraZeneca/University of Oxford [14,15] indicates that the conclusions of this Report is correct. The study of Mlcochova, P. et al. [16] shows that the neutralization of SARS-COV-2 variant B.1.617.2 from India by neutralizing antibodies from AZD1222 vaccinated individuals was much reduced. That the United States FDA has so far refused to approve the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine (AZD1222) developed by AstraZeneca/University of Oxford [3,17] says a lot about the efficacy and safety of the said vaccine. The oblivious, contradictious and flip-flopping Director of the United States even accused AstraZeneca/University of Oxford of committing Dishonest Scientific Reporting and Data Falsification [3].

References.

1. United States National Institutes of Health New Releases (2021) Issue of March 22, 2021 (<https://www.nih.gov/news-events/news-releases/investigational-astrazeneca-vaccine-prevents-covid-19>).
Investigational AstraZeneca vaccine prevents COVID-19.
2. AstraZeneca Website (2021) Issue of March 22, 2021.
(<https://www.astrazeneca.com/media-centre/press-releases/2021/astrazeneca-us-vaccine-trial-met-primary-endpoint.html>).
AZD1222 US Phase III trial met primary efficacy endpoint in preventing COVID-19 at interim analysis.
3. Meredith, S. (2021) CNBC Heath and Science. Issue of March 23, 2021.
AstraZeneca may have included outdated information in Covid vaccine trial, U.S. Health agency says.

4. . Tung, H.Y.L. (2020) in In the Matter of Scientific Misconduct and Fraud by H.Y. LimTung, Chapter One, pp5-26, Cactoa Scientific Publishers, Inc., New York City (Astoria), New York, U.S.A.
Definition of Scientific Misconduct, Scientific Fraud and Dishonest Scientific Report.
5. Tung, H.Y.L. (2019) J. Invest. Cri. Pub. Sci. Articles, Vol. 1, pp6-20.
Scientific Misconduct, Scientific Fraud and Dishonest Scientific Report.
6. Keith, T. (2021) NPR Politics, Issue of March 19, 2021.
Biden takes first jab at vaccine diplomacy, sharing doses with Mexico and Canada.
7. Volsey, M. et al. (2021) Lancet, Vol. 397, pp99-111.
Safety and efficacy of the ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 vaccine (AZD1222) against SARS-CoV-2: an interim analysis of four randomised controlled trials in Brazil, South Africa, and the UK.
8. Polack, F.P. et al. (2020) New Engl. J. Med., Vol. 383, pp2603-2615.
Safety and efficacy of the BNT162b2 mRNA Covid-19 vaccine.
9. Baden, L.R. et al. (2021) New Engl. J. Med., Vol. 384, pp403-416.
Efficacy and safety of the mRNA-1273 SARS-CoV-2 vaccine.
10. Sadoff, J. (2021) New Engl. J. Med., DOI: 10.1056/NEJMoa2101544.
Safety and efficacy of single-dose Ad26.COV2.S vaccine against Covid-19.
11. Tung, H.Y.L. (2021) New Biomed. Sci., Vol. 2, pp34-54
SARS-COV-2 Infection and Virulence: Are the Anti-SARS-COV-2 Vaccines developed by Pfizer/BioNTech, Moderna and Johnson & Johnson Effective and and Safe?
12. Walach, H. et al. (2021) Vaccines, DOI: 10.3390/vaccines9070693.
The safety of COVID-19 vaccinations-We should rethink the policy.
13. Tung, H.Y.L. (2021) J. Invest. Cri. Pub. Sci. Articles, Vol. 4, pp6-17.
Did the authors of the paper entitled "The safety of COVID-19 vaccinations-We should rethink the policy", published then retracted in Vaccines [Walach, H. et al. (2021) Vaccines, DOI: 10.3390/vaccines9070693] mis-interpreted and distorted available scientific data?
14. Le Page, M. et al. (2021) New Scientist, Issue of July 19, 2021.
Covid-19 news: England unlocks as UK cases continue to soar.
15. Douglas, J. and Fidler, S. (2021) Wall Street Journal, Issue of July 2, 2021.
Some vaccinated people are dying of Covid-19. Here's why scientists aren't surprised.
16. Mlcochova, P. et al. (2021) Research Square, DOI:10.21203/rs.3rs-637724/v1.
SARS-CoV-2 B.6172 Delta variant emergence and vaccine breakthrough.
17. Boseley, S. (2021) The Guardian, Issue of June 26, 2021.
The Oxford vaccine: the trials and tribulations of a world-saving jab.